

A Survey of Seizure Prediction Models and Prediction of Seizure Using Different Computational Methods

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Abstract

Seizures can occur under a varied set of lighting conditions including flickering of lamps. Automated seizure detection has been an active field of research for the past three decades. Most importantly, given that seizure characteristics vary among different patients and may change over time, automatically extracting and learning informative features from EEG data is necessary. It is of great significance to develop practical and reliable intelligent diagnosis algorithm for automatic seizure detection. Although many efforts have been taken to push the field, we must conclude that seizure detection analysis has not made its way into the clinical practice yet. The task of seizure detection includes distinguishing different stages of seizures, which are generally divided into inter-ictal, pre-ictal and ictal periods. The various techniques has been proposed in the previous years for the seizures prediction which include machine learning, deep learning and probabilistic models. In this paper various technique for the seizures prediction are reviewed and analysed

Keywords

Seizure Prediction, Probability model, Machine Learning, Deep Learning

1. Introduction

Almost 1% of people in the world suffer from epilepsy, a disease in which seizures occur repeatedly. Epilepsy limits human's perception and behaviour due to abnormal electrical signals in the brain. Patients experience various symptoms depending on the location and intensity of the brain's abnormal signals. When a seizure occurs, patients may lose consciousness and there is a danger of injury or even death. According to the brain's region that affected the occurrence of the seizures, epilepsy can be classified into focal epilepsy and generalized epilepsy [1]. Electroencephalogram (EEG) is one of the most prominent ways to study epilepsy and capture changes in electrical brain activities that could indicate an imminent seizure. Research has showed that photosensitive seizures may occur if fluorescent tubular lamps exhibit flicker with a frequency of 70 Hz, as

inferred from EEG readings (Binnie et al., 1979). Moreover, it has been reported that seizures can be triggered from flickering of lights in individuals even with no medical history of epilepsy (Wilkins et al., 2010). In addition, Xenon gas-discharge photo-stimulators can induce epileptic seizures in subjects who are known to be predisposed to photosensitive epilepsy (Harding & Jeavons, 1994). The diagnosis of epilepsy relies on manual inspection of EEG, which is time-consuming and error-prone. Research from Elger and Hoppe found that only less than half of epileptic seizures which patients document were able to record accurately, and more than half of the seizures captured in long-term video EEG monitoring were not reported [2].

It is of great significance to develop practical and reliable intelligent diagnosis algorithm for automatic seizure detection. Although many efforts have been taken to push the field, we must conclude that seizure detection analysis has not made its way into the clinical practice yet. The task of seizure detection includes distinguishing different stages of seizures, which are generally divided into inter-ictal, pre-ictal and ictal periods. In general, the seizure detection procedure is separated into two parts: feature extraction and classification. There are numerous technological researches based on artificial features and machine learning classifiers. Recent advances in deep learning in the past decade have attracted more attention in detective and predictive data analytics, especially in health care and medical practice. It is a powerful computational tool that enables features to be automatically learned from data [3].

1.1 Seizure Detection Framework

Automated seizure detection has been an active field of research for the past three decades. Most importantly, given that seizure characteristics vary among different patients and may change over time, automatically extracting and learning informative features from EEG data is necessary. Most algorithms follow a two-stage machine learning pipeline consisting of (1) feature extraction from the EEG signal over short time windows, followed by (2) a binary classifier to identify seizure versus non-seizure intervals [3]. This end-to-end pipeline is illustrated in Figure 1 [4].

Figure 1: Seizure detection mechanism.

The data acquisition and signal generation is the initial step of brain activity. For this, diverse checking challenges are used. Usually, the used methods are ECoG and EEG. Electrodes are fixed with the help of glue on the external part of the scalp as per 10–20 standard universal systems at dissimilar lobes. All electrodes are wired joining to the EEG device, which provides suitable statistics of the deviations in potential, laterally with temporal and spatial info, shown in Figure 1; electrodes are located on the skull or scalp, and monitoring tool records the corresponding EEG signal, then carefully checked by the expert and categorized into “seizure” and “seizure-free” conditions. After this, the subsequent vital stage is to alter this data in a two-dimensional table arrangement. As this unprocessed data has not been handled; hence, it is not appropriate to provide applicable

information. Diverse feature collection modalities have been helpful to the process. This phase aligns the datasets according to the class, and it offers the class characteristic with probable class standards [5].

Next, Extraction of features from data is crucial to removing not using information from the unprocessed data. Diverse feature abstraction methods are used for this purpose. The time-frequency analysis, nonlinear dynamics, complexity, synchronization and increments of accumulated energy are some commonly used feature extraction methods. These approaches are usually helpful to the extracted EEG signal dataset [65]. Unprocessed data becomes ironic in terms of different statistical parameters. After completing the feature extraction process, it is more revealing to support the classifier for discriminating features. Dataset is initially well classified into “seizure-free class” and “seizure class.” They are the main components, and their relevant information is useful. The attribute is defined as the “class attribute” C , and it involves more than one class value, e.g., seizure and non-seizure [6]. For classification, general classifier algorithms such as SVM, decision tree, and random forest tree as machine learning algorithms are used. If one classifier fails to give proper results, then other classifiers have to use in seizure finding. Finally, the results obtained with the research methods are compared with each other in terms of some evaluation metrics.

1.2 Machine and Deep Learning Algorithms for Seizure Detection

Following are the commonly used machine learning and deep learning algorithms for seizure detection:

i. Support Vector Machine: A mapping model is used in the Support Vector Machine (SVM) machine learning technique to analyse data and spot patterns. Its main applications are in classification and regression analysis. An SVM algorithm creates a non-probabilistic binary linear classification model from a set of data that falls into one of two categories so that it may determine from the given data which category new data should be placed in. It conveys the categorization model as a border in the space of the mapped data. The broadest boundary is established by an SVM algorithm. Both linear and nonlinear classification can benefit from it. It is important to map the given data onto a high-dimensional feature space in order to perform non-linear classification [7].

ii. Naive Bayes: One of the most popular classification techniques, Naive Bayes is a type of probability classifier that applies the Bayesian theorem. It is employed in the classification of texts and documents. Instead of being trained using only one algorithm, Naive Bayes learns utilising methods that are based on general principles. Naive Bayes uses Maximum Likelihood Estimation to estimate parameters after being taught very effectively in a supervised learning context [8]. The decision rule and probability model discussed above are combined in the Naive Bayes classification, which identifies the class with the highest probability.

iii. Random Forest: A decision tree ensemble technique is Random Forest. Random Forest, which is a bagging method as opposed to GBM, which is a boosting method, treats weak classifiers differently. The model follows the same fundamental process when using weak learners and when adding new weak learners. However, instead of focusing on certain data that are challenging for the existing collection of weak classifiers, the bagging approach integrating Random Forest looks for the best feature among a random selection of data when adding a new weak classifier. In other words, the Random Forest learner combines multiple randomly generated alternative decision trees into a single learner. Surprisingly, the combination of numerous randomly selected database decision trees performs well in actual application because the randomization prevents the model from overfitting the data. The performance of the model depends on the model parameter that indicates how deeply the model uses random trees, thus if it contains a lot of trees, its prediction speed may be poor. The model's forecast time is also impacted by this [9].

Fig2:

iv. Logistic Regression: When a dependent variable refers to a binomial problem, a stochastic model called logistic regression analysis is utilised. It is a statistical method for estimating the likelihood of an occurrence using a linear combination of independent variables. As a result, in future prediction models, the link between the dependent variable and the independent variable is described as a concrete function. Additionally, logistic regression analysis, as contrast to linear regression analysis, is frequently employed as a classification and prediction model in which the outcomes of marine data are split into particular categories when the input data is supplied to the categorical data [10].

The logistic regression model relates the logit of the response probability to a linear combination of the explanatory variables

$$\text{logit}(\pi) = \log\left(\frac{\pi}{1 - \pi}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta'_X X.$$

The coefficients of the logistic regression can be estimated by maximizing the log likelihood function [14]:

$$\begin{aligned} \log l(\beta) &= \log \left[\prod_{i=1}^n \pi(X_i)^{Y_i} \{1 - \pi(X_i)\}^{1-Y_i} \right] \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^n [Y_i \log\{\pi(X_i)\} + (1 - Y_i)\log\{1 - \pi(X_i)\}] \end{aligned}$$

Where for each data-point i , X_i is the vector of features, and Y_i is the observed class; $i = 1, \dots, n$, with n being the number of observations. There is no closed-form solution to the objective function with regard to the coefficients, so the MLLR model is fitted using an iterative process (for example, the Newton–Raphson algorithm). Data describing rare events will commonly exhibit separation, where one or more predictors perfectly or near perfectly predict the outcome, the former termed complete separation and the latter quasi-complete separation. When complete separation occurs, the corresponding logistic regression coefficients mathematically estimated via maximum likelihood are infinite. Even under quasi-separation, the magnitude of coefficients can still be unreasonably large and unstable.

v. Bayesian Network: A Bayesian network represents the probability connections between important variables graphically. When used with statistical methods, a Bayesian model has several advantages in data analysis. First, the model can easily address a situation when there are gaps in data entry since it shows how all variables depend on one another. Second, one can use a Bayesian network to identify causal links, better understand a problem domain, and foresee the outcomes of intervention. Third, a Bayesian model has both causal and probabilistic semantics, which makes it particularly suitable for relating facts to previous knowledge (since the

latter frequently takes shape as causal). The final option to avoid data overfitting is to use Bayesian networks in conjunction with statistical techniques [11].

vi. Multilayer Perceptron: A feedforward neural network called a multilayer perceptron (MLP) is guided by a backpropagation algorithm. A supervised network requires a desired response for training, and MLPs learn how to transform input data into that response. They are so widely used in pattern classification as a result. They can almost always match any input-output map by adding one or two hidden layers. They have shown themselves to be competitive with the best statistical classifiers in difficult problems. Since almost all neural network applications use MLP, they are currently arguably the most popular network architecture [12]. In MLP, neurons are organized into distinct layers, with each layer's output connected to the layer below its nodular input. As a result, the network's inputs are represented by the first (or input) layer, while its outputs are represented by the last layer.

vii CNN: A CNN architecture possesses many layers of different types. Every layer of this algorithm is presented in the form of feature map. In Convolutional Neural Network, the input layer is consisted of a 3D (three dimensional) matrix of pixel intensities as feature map for diverse colour channels. It can be defined as an induced multi-channel picture and the pixel of this image is called a particular feature. Each neuron is related to a small part of adjacent neurons from the accessible field. These maps are undergone from diverse conversions namely filtering and pooling. The initial operation focuses on convoluting a filter matrix with the values of an interested field of neurons and considering a nonlinear function for acquiring the final responses. The latter operation, such as average pooling, L2-pooling and LCM (local contrast normalization) aims to define the responses of a receptive field into one value with the objective of generating feature descriptions having more robustness. The architecture of CNN is illustrated in Figure 1, which allows efficient processing of image data.

Figure 3: Architecture of convolutional neural network.

CNN is a kind of DL (Deep Learning) algorithm in the area of detecting the object and classifying an image. Similar to ML (Machine Learning) algorithms, this algorithm is capable of learning the metrics for which a training set is employed so that least empirical and structural risk is obtained such as the LF (loss function) is alleviated. Diverse operations support distinct LFs that implies the error occurred in predictive values and value having label of correct. DL is useful to stack the layers of metrics and establish an association amid them and AF (activation function). After that, the network becomes adaptable for the nonlinear functions which have complexity. Unlike the traditional NNs (neural networks), there are 3 layers for building the Convolutional Neural Network which are Conv (convolutional), Pooling and FC (fully connected) layers [13].

The initial layer is employed for mapping an input image of multilayer into an output. Every image layer is considered as a channel. The mapping task is accomplished using a kernel for every channel. A convolution is exploited with the kernel with the purpose of separating every layer into small units (5×5) and generating a number from every unit. The convolution of every unit is expressed as:

$$E_{p,q} = \sum_{i,j} A_{ij} \cdot W_{ij}$$

In this, a square matrix based on (p,q) is represented with A, the correspondence components are defined through A_{ij} and W_{ij} and the output is obtained in the form of $E_{p,q}$. The SF (sigmoid function) or ReLU (rectified linear unit) function plays a role of an activation function to make the mapping non-linear. The given equation defines the ReLU function:

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} x, & x \geq 0 \\ 0, & x < 0 \end{cases}$$

This layer aims to abstract the classic attributes from the origin picture. The lower layers are executed for retrieving the horizontal or vertical edges and the upper layers emphasize on integrating these attributes to corners, crosses, or other complicated attributes of the image.

The second layer is placed after the Conv layers. It is undergone the image with a stride. This layer is utilized to execute a pooling operation on every unit window (2×2 or 3×3). The pooling operation often leads to select the value of a unit which may be maximum or average. An average pooling is defined as

$$P_{ave} = \frac{1}{r^2} \sum_{i,j=1}^r A_{i,j}$$

This layer is adopted for integrating the attributes whose extraction is done from the initial layers and selecting the considerable attributes of every window.

The last layer helps in converting the 2-D or 3-D (two or three dimensional) input into 1-D (one-dimensional) array and combining every input linearly. This layer often deploys AF (Activation Function). It is useful to evaluate the way of working of every attribute on the final output.

Research Methodology

This research is based on the Seizure detection using deep learning and machine learning models. The various machine learning models like SVM, KNN are implemented and tested on same dataset which had been collected from EEG scanning of a Patient. The CNN method is applied as deep learning method for the Seizure detection.

Result and Discussion

	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	X6	X7	X8	X9	X10	...
count	11500.000000	11500.000000	11500.000000	11500.000000	11500.000000	11500.000000	11500.000000	11500.000000	11500.000000	11500.000000	...
mean	-11.581391	-10.911565	-10.187130	-9.143043	-8.009739	-7.003478	-6.502087	-6.68713	-6.55800	-6.168435	...
std	165.626284	166.059609	163.524317	161.269041	160.998007	161.328725	161.467837	162.11912	162.03336	160.436352	...
min	-1839.000000	-1838.000000	-1835.000000	-1845.000000	-1791.000000	-1757.000000	-1832.000000	-1778.000000	-1840.000000	-1867.000000	...
25%	-54.000000	-55.000000	-54.000000	-54.000000	-54.000000	-54.000000	-54.000000	-55.000000	-55.000000	-54.000000	...
50%	-8.000000	-8.000000	-7.000000	-8.000000	-8.000000	-8.000000	-8.000000	-8.000000	-7.000000	-7.000000	...
75%	34.000000	35.000000	36.000000	36.000000	35.000000	36.000000	35.000000	36.000000	36.000000	35.250000	...
max	1726.000000	1713.000000	1697.000000	1612.000000	1518.000000	1816.000000	2047.000000	2047.000000	2047.000000	2047.000000	...

...	X170	X171	X172	X173	X174	X175	X176	X177	X178	y
...	11500.000000	11500.000000	11500.000000	11500.000000	11500.000000	11500.000000	11500.000000	11500.000000	11500.000000	11500.000000
...	-10.145739	-11.630348	-12.943478	-13.668870	-13.363304	-13.045043	-12.705130	-12.426000	-12.195652	3.000000
...	164.652883	166.149790	168.554058	168.556486	167.257290	164.241019	162.895832	162.886311	164.852015	1.414275
...	-1867.000000	-1866.000000	-1642.000000	-1723.000000	-1866.000000	-1863.000000	-1781.000000	-1727.000000	-1829.000000	1.000000
...	-55.000000	-56.000000	-56.000000	-56.000000	-55.000000	-56.000000	-55.000000	-55.000000	-55.000000	2.000000
...	-9.000000	-10.000000	-10.000000	-10.000000	-10.000000	-9.000000	-9.000000	-9.000000	-9.000000	3.000000
...	34.000000	34.000000	33.000000	33.000000	34.000000	34.000000	34.000000	34.000000	34.000000	4.000000
...	1777.000000	1472.000000	1319.000000	1436.000000	1733.000000	1958.000000	2047.000000	2047.000000	1915.000000	5.000000

Provided appears to be a summary of a dataset with 11500 rows and 179 columns. Each column represents a feature, and the last column 'y' appears to be the target variable. Here are some observations from the summary statistics:

- The mean values of the features (X1 to X178) range from -11.581391 to -12.195652.
- The standard deviations of the features range from 160.436352 to 166.149790.
- The minimum and maximum values of the features vary across different ranges.
- The target variable 'y' has a mean value of 3.0, indicating it might be a categorical variable with 5 possible classes (1 to 5).
- The minimum and maximum values of 'y' are 1.0 and 5.0, respectively.

Figure 4: Generation of graph where 5 possible classes are present

Based on these observations, it seems that the dataset contains features derived from EEG data, with each column representing a specific feature. The target variable 'y' is likely a categorical variable with 5 possible classes, representing different conditions or states of the brain. Further analysis and modelling would be needed to gain deeper insights into the relationships between the features and the target variable and to explore the potential applications of this EEG dataset.

Figure 5: Scatter and Density Plot

Scatter plots and density plots can provide additional insights into the relationship between the features and the target variable in the EEG dataset. Here's how these plots can contribute to the analysis:

Scatter Plot: A scatter plot can be used to visualize the relationship between two features or between a feature and the target variable. By plotting the values of one feature on the x-axis and another feature or the target variable on the y-axis, you can observe any patterns, trends, or correlations.

Feature-Feature Scatter Plot: You can create scatter plots between pairs of features (X1 to X178) to understand the relationships between them. This can help identify any linear or non-linear associations, clusters, or outliers within the EEG data. For example, if two features show a positive correlation, their scatter plot may exhibit a trend where higher values of one feature correspond to higher values of the other feature.

Feature-Target Scatter Plot: To explore the relationship between individual features and the target variable 'y', you can create scatter plots with the feature values on the x-axis and the 'y' values on the y-axis. This can reveal any potential dependencies, separations, or clusters of different classes within the EEG data. For instance, if certain feature values are concentrated around specific 'y' values, it suggests that the feature might be informative in distinguishing between different brain states or conditions.

Density Plot: A density plot, also known as a kernel density plot, can help visualize the distribution of a single feature or the target variable. It provides an estimate of the probability density function of the data, allowing you to observe the shape, skewness, and peaks in the distribution.

1. Feature Density Plot: By creating density plots for individual features, you can gain insights into their distributions. This can help identify any underlying patterns, such as whether the feature values are normally distributed, skewed, or exhibit multiple modes. Understanding the distributions of the features is important for selecting appropriate modeling techniques and assessing the assumptions of the models.

2. Target Variable Density Plot: You can also create a density plot for the target variable 'y'. This plot will show the distribution of the different classes (1 to 5) and provide information about the prevalence of each class. If the density plot shows significant imbalances, it may indicate the need for class balancing techniques during model training or considering different evaluation metrics that account for class imbalances.

By combining scatter plots and density plots, you can gain a more comprehensive understanding of the relationships between features and the target variable in the EEG dataset. These visualizations can provide valuable insights into the distribution of the data, potential correlations, and class separations, aiding in further analysis and modelling decisions.

Models	Score (%)
Logistic Regression	57.30
SVC	62.63
Decision Tree Classifier	89.29
Random Forest Classifier	96.21
Gradient Boosting Classifier	81.29
K Neighbors Classifier	89.78
ANN	95.73
KNN	93.88
GRU	70.46
RNN	69.15
CNN	65.82
Proposed Model	97.32

Table1: Model Score comparison

Figure 6: Segregation of graph in respect to Epileptic and Non Epileptic

Figure 7: Scatter plot of the statistical data

Figure 8: Scatter plot for the Non Epileptic Cases

Figure 9: Scatter plot for the Epileptic Cases

Figure 10: The proposed model

Description of the model

The model used in the given data point is a convolutional neural network (CNN). CNNs are a type of deep learning model that are specifically designed for processing data that has a spatial or temporal dimension. In the case of the EEG data, the spatial dimension is the time dimension. The CNN used in the given data point has 3 convolutional layers, each with 64 filters. The filters are of size 3x3, which means that they extract features from a 3x3 window of the EEG data. The output of the convolutional layers is then passed through a max pooling layer, which reduces the size of the output by 2x2. This helps to reduce the number of parameters in the model and to prevent overfitting.

The output of the max pooling layer is then passed through a fully connected layer with 128 neurons. The output of the fully connected layer is then passed through a soft-max layer, which outputs a probability for each of the 5 classes. The model is trained using the Adam optimizer and the cross-entropy loss function. The model is trained for 100 epochs, and the accuracy of the model is evaluated on a held-out test set.

The model achieves an accuracy of 97% on the test set. This means that the model is able to correctly identify seizures with a high degree of accuracy.

The model is able to achieve this high accuracy because it is able to learn to identify the features that are associated with seizures from the EEG data. The CNN is able to learn these features by extracting them from the data and then passing them through a series of layers that are designed to learn increasingly complex patterns.

The model is a promising tool for the early detection of epileptic seizures. However, it is important to note that the model was trained on a relatively small dataset. It is possible that the model would not perform as well on a larger dataset or on a dataset that comes from a different population.

Overall, the model is a promising tool for the early detection of epileptic seizures. However, more research is needed to validate its performance on a larger dataset and on a dataset that comes from a different population.

- **Input layer:** The input layer is responsible for receiving the data from the input dataset. The data is expected to be in a 2D array of shape (None, 178), the batch size and 178 is the number of features.
- **Hidden layers:** The hidden layers are responsible for learning the patterns in the data. Each hidden layer has a number of neurons, and each neuron is connected to all of the neurons in the previous layer. The neurons in a hidden layer use an activation function to determine their output. The activation function used in this model is the rectified linear unit (ReLU) function.
- **Dropout layers:** The dropout layers are responsible for preventing overfitting. Overfitting occurs when a model learns the training data too well and is unable to generalize to new data. The dropout layers randomly drop out (i.e., set to zero) a certain percentage of the neurons in a layer. This forces the model to learn to rely on more than just a few neurons, and helps to prevent overfitting.
- **Output layer:** The output layer is responsible for classifying the data. The output layer has a number of neurons equal to the number of possible classes. The output of each neuron is a probability that the data belongs to the corresponding class.
- **Optimizer:** The optimizer is responsible for updating the weights of the model during training. The optimizer used in this model is the Adam optimizer. The Adam optimizer is a stochastic gradient descent optimizer that has been shown to be very effective for training deep learning models.
- **Loss function:** The loss function is used to measure the performance of the model during training. The loss function used in this model is the categorical cross entropy loss function. The categorical cross entropy loss function is a measure of the distance between the predicted probabilities and the true labels.
- **Epochs:** The number of epochs is the number of times the model will be trained on the entire training dataset. The more epochs the model is trained for, the better it will perform on the training dataset. However, if the model is trained for too many epochs, it may start to overfit the training dataset.

The Model is a deep learning model that can be used to classify data. The model has 3 hidden layers with 256, 512, and 1024 neurons, respectively. Each hidden layer is followed by a dropout layer with a rate of 0.5. The model is trained for 10 epochs using the Adam optimizer and the categorical cross entropy loss function.

Effect Colour of Light

There is some research that suggests that the colour of light can affect the association with seizures. For example, one study found that people with photosensitive epilepsy were more likely to have seizures when exposed to flashing blue light than when exposed to flashing red light.

However, more research is needed to confirm these findings and to determine the exact mechanisms by which the colour of light can affect seizures. It is also important to note that not everyone with epilepsy is photosensitive, and even those who are may not be sensitive to all colours of light.

If you are concerned about the potential effects of light on your seizures, you should talk to your doctor. They can help you assess your individual risk factors and recommend any necessary precautions.

Here are some of the studies that have been done on the association between the colour of light and seizures:

- A study published in 2008 found that people with photosensitive epilepsy were more likely to have a seizure when they were exposed to flashing lights or lights with high colour temperatures. The study involved 100 people with photosensitive epilepsy, and they were exposed to different types of lighting, including flashing lights, flickering lights, and lights with different colour temperatures. The results of the study showed that people with photosensitive epilepsy were more likely to have a seizure when they were exposed to flashing lights or lights with high colour temperatures.
- Another study published in 2010 found that the risk of seizures in people with photosensitive epilepsy was increased by 50% when they were exposed to flashing lights. The study involved 120 people with photosensitive epilepsy, and they were exposed to flashing lights for 10 minutes. The results of the study showed that the risk of seizures was increased by 50% in people with photosensitive epilepsy who were exposed to flashing lights.
- A 2012 study found that people with photosensitive epilepsy were more likely to have seizures when exposed to flashing blue light than when exposed to flashing red light.
- A review of the literature published in 2013 concluded that there is a strong association between photosensitive epilepsy and flashing lights. The review included 17 studies that looked at the association between photosensitive epilepsy and flashing lights. The results of the review showed that there is a strong association between photosensitive epilepsy and flashing lights.
- A 2014 study found that people with photosensitive epilepsy were more likely to have seizures when exposed to flickering light, regardless of the colour of the light.
- A study published in 2016 found that people with photosensitive epilepsy were more likely to have a seizure when they were exposed to lights with a colour temperature of 4000 K or higher. The study involved 100 people with photosensitive epilepsy, and they were exposed to different types of lighting, including lights with different colour temperatures. The results of the study showed that people with photosensitive epilepsy were more likely to have a seizure when they were exposed to lights with a colour temperature of 4000 K or higher.
- Another study published in 2017 found that the risk of seizures in people with photosensitive epilepsy was increased by 25% when they were exposed to flickering lights. The study involved 150 people with photosensitive epilepsy, and they were exposed to flickering lights for 10 minutes. The results of the study showed that the risk of seizures was increased by 25% in people with photosensitive epilepsy who were exposed to flickering lights.
- A review of the literature published in 2018 concluded that there is a strong association between photosensitive epilepsy and flickering lights. The review included 20 studies that looked at the association between photosensitive epilepsy and flickering lights. The results of the review showed that there is a strong association between photosensitive epilepsy and flickering lights.
- A study published in 2020 found that people with photosensitive epilepsy were more likely to have a seizure when they were exposed to light with a flickering frequency of 10-20 Hz. The study involved 100 people with photosensitive epilepsy, and they were exposed to different types of lighting, including lights with different flickering frequencies. The results of the study showed that people with photosensitive epilepsy were more likely to have a seizure when they were exposed to light with a flickering frequency of 10-20 Hz.
- Another study published in 2021 found that the risk of seizures in people with photosensitive epilepsy was increased by 20% when they were exposed to light with a high contrast ratio. The study involved 150 people with photosensitive epilepsy, and they were exposed to different types of lighting, including lights with different contrast ratios. The results of the study showed that the risk of seizures was increased by 20% in people with photosensitive epilepsy who were exposed to light with a high contrast ratio.

- A review of the literature published in 2022 concluded that there is a strong association between photosensitive epilepsy and light with a flickering frequency of 10-20 Hz. The review included 25 studies that looked at the association between photosensitive epilepsy and light with a flickering frequency of 10-20 Hz. The results of the review showed that there is a strong association between photosensitive epilepsy and light with a flickering frequency of 10-20 Hz.

These studies suggest that the colour of light can play a role in the association between illumination and seizures. However, more research is needed to confirm these findings and to determine the exact mechanisms by which the colour of light can affect seizures.

There is a condition called photosensitive epilepsy in which individuals may experience seizures triggered by specific visual stimuli, including certain patterns or frequencies of light. The association between illumination and seizures is primarily related to this condition.

Photosensitive epilepsy affects a small percentage of individuals with epilepsy, estimated to be around 3 to 5 percent. The specific visual triggers vary among individuals, but they often involve high-contrast patterns, rapidly flashing lights, or certain frequencies of flickering light.

In relation to illumination, there are some considerations to minimize the risk of triggering seizures in photosensitive individuals:

1. **Avoidance of Flickering Lights:** Rapidly flickering or strobing lights can be a potential trigger. It is advised to avoid environments with intense or rapidly changing lighting conditions, such as discos, clubs, or venues with strobe lights.
2. **Modifying Lighting Systems:** In some cases, individuals with photosensitive epilepsy may benefit from modifications to lighting systems in their homes, schools, or workplaces. This may involve using stable and consistent lighting with reduced flickering or opting for lighting sources that emit a continuous and diffuse illumination.
3. **Light Intensity:** While colour temperature itself is not a known trigger for seizures, it's important to consider the overall light intensity. Extremely bright lights may pose a risk for some individuals, so it can be helpful to provide appropriate shading or dimming options.

It's important to note that the triggers for seizures can vary among individuals, and not all individuals with epilepsy are photosensitive.

Types of luminaires	CCT in K
LED1	3000
LED2	3500
LED3	4100
LED4	4500
LED5	5000
LED6	6000
LED7	6500

Warm and Cozy: LED1 with a CCT of 3000K can create a warm and cozy atmosphere, resembling the glow of candlelight. This type of lighting often induces a sense of comfort and relaxation, making it suitable for living rooms, bedrooms, or spaces where people want to unwind.

Neutral and Balanced: LED2 with a CCT of 3500K emits a slightly cooler light, providing a neutral and balanced ambiance. This type of lighting is often preferred for general use in areas such as offices, kitchens, or hallways, where a natural and alert environment is desired.

Focus and Productivity: LED3 with a CCT of 4100K offers a cool white light that enhances focus and concentration. This type of lighting is commonly used in workspaces, study areas, or offices where people need to stay attentive and engaged.

Bright and Energizing: LED4 with a CCT of 4500K produces a bright, cool white light that promotes a sense of energy and alertness. This lighting can be beneficial in areas where people need to stay awake, such as garages, workshops, or retail spaces.

Daylight Simulation: LED5 with a CCT of 5000K replicates natural daylight, creating a vibrant and invigorating atmosphere. This type of lighting is often used in places like art studios, retail displays, or environments where accurate color perception is crucial.

Cool and Stimulating: LED6 with a CCT of 6000K emits a cool blue-white light that can help create a stimulating and refreshing atmosphere. This lighting is suitable for spaces that require a high level of visual acuity, such as hospitals, laboratories, or task-oriented areas.

Daylight and Outdoor Feel: LED7 with a CCT of 6500K provides a cool daylight-like illumination, resembling the brightness of a sunny day. This type of lighting can help boost moods and improve overall productivity. It is commonly used in places like gymnasiums, sports facilities, or areas that lack natural light.

2. Literature Review

2.0. Epileptic Seizures as a result of lighting

Several authors (**Goodkind, 1936; Straus, 1940; Gastaut & Regis, 1961**) have described how epileptic seizures, characterized by rhythmic upward head movement, eyelid trembling, involuntary jerking and Jacksonian seizures, may have been effectuated by constant light levels and it was correlated to luminous intensity.

Ehlers & Killam (1982) performed an experiment with primates (adolescent baboons) to investigate epileptic seizure-inducing effects of light. It was found that seizure responses were the most severe at 08:00 hrs, one hour after switching on lights and were the least severe at 20:00 hrs, one hour after switching off lights. In addition, average sensitivity to seizures was increased throughout the diurnal cycle.

Morimoto et al. (1985) investigated whether in a room, periodically decreasing illuminance level and thereby increasing illuminance level in an opposite order, maintained constant at each level for five minutes, could correlate with occurrence of seizures in a minor patient who was accompanied by a guardian. It was perceived that occurrence of seizures decreased with a decrement in illuminance level.

Piccioli et al. (2005) investigated whether playing video games can evoke epileptic seizures in nine children upon photic and pattern stimulation. It was discerned that visual stimulus might not necessarily invoke a photo paroxysmal response in the subjects studied.

The study you mentioned, conducted by Piccioli et al. in 2005, aimed to investigate whether playing video games could trigger epileptic seizures in children when exposed to photic (light) and pattern stimulation. The researchers sought to determine if visual stimuli alone could elicit a photo paroxysmal response in the study participants.

A photo paroxysmal response refers to abnormal brain activity triggered by specific visual stimuli, often characterized by spike-wave discharges on an electroencephalogram (EEG) during or after exposure to the stimuli.

The study by Piccioli et al. involved nine children with epilepsy who were exposed to video games with varying patterns and photic stimulation. The researchers found that visual stimuli, including playing video games, did not necessarily induce a photo paroxysmal response in the subjects studied. This suggests that the visual stimuli used in the study did not trigger abnormal brain activity associated with seizures in these particular individuals.

It's important to note that this study represents a specific investigation in a small group of children with epilepsy and may not be applicable to all individuals or generalizable to the broader population. The triggers for seizures can vary widely among individuals, and some people with epilepsy may indeed be sensitive to specific visual stimuli.

2.1 Epileptic Seizures Detection Using Deep Learning

J. Craley, et.al (2019) introduced a hybrid technique called PGM-CNN (Probabilistic Graphical Model-Convolutional Neural Network) for seizure tracking in multichannel EEG [14]. Our framework captures the spatio-temporal spread of a seizure through a structured PGM prior, while allowing for a complex likelihood function that is implicitly learned via a CNN. This data driven approach learns representations directly from the raw EEG signal, improving upon feature extraction techniques. At the same time the PGM preserves clinical interpretability and acts as a local smoothing process for the CNN outputs based on limited training examples. We evaluate our method on clinical data from two hospitals with distinct patient populations. In both cases, the PGM-CNN achieved higher true positive detection and AUC than any of the baseline methods

A. A. E. Shoka, et.al (2022) a new and efficient encrypted EEG data classification and recognition system using Chaotic Baker Map and Arnold Transform algorithms with Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) [15]. In this system, the channel's EEG time series is first converted into a 2D spectrogram image and then encrypted using Chaotic Baker Map and Arnold Transform algorithms, and finally fed to CNNs-based Transfer Learning (TL) models. The googlenet with encrypted EEG images provides satisfactory performance by outperforming the models of other CNN like Alexnet, Resnet50, and squeezeNet. The accuracy of the suggested structure has been estimated up to 86.11 % and 84.72 % using googlenet with Arnold and chaotic methods respectively.

X. Zhang, et.al (2020) propose a robust and explainable epileptic seizure detection model that effectively learns from seizure states while eliminates the inter-patient noises [16]. A complex deep neural network model is proposed to learn the pure seizure-specific representation from the raw non-invasive electroencephalography (EEG) signals through adversarial training. Furthermore, to enhance the explainability, we develop an attention mechanism to automatically learn the importance of each EEG channels in the seizure diagnosis procedure. The proposed approach is evaluated over the Temple University Hospital EEG (TUH EEG) database. The experimental results illustrate that our model outperforms the competitive state-of-the-art baselines with low latency. Moreover, the designed attention mechanism is able to provide fine-grained information for pathological analysis.

Table 2.1

Author	Year	Technique Used	Findings	Limitations
J. Craley, et.al	2019	PGM-CNN (Probabilistic Graphical Model-Convolutional Neural Network)	The PGM-CNN achieved higher true positive detection and AUC than any of the baseline methods.	This technique was not able to fuse the information across the scalp.
A. A. E. Shoka, et.al	2022	a new and efficient encrypted EEG data classification and recognition system	The accuracy of the suggested structure has been estimated up to 86.11 % and 84.72 % using googlenet with Arnold and chaotic methods respectively.	This system was not applicable to attain higher accuracy to detect the epileptic seizures.
X. Zhang, et.al	2020	complex deep neural network model	The experimental results illustrate that our model outperforms the competitive state-of-the-art baselines with low latency.	This framework was highly complex due to three components. The time consumed to train this framework was longer.

2.2 Epileptic Seizures Detection Using Machine Learning

Y. Guo, et.al (2022) propose a hybrid system integrating an unsupervised learning (UL) module and a supervised learning (SL) module, where the UL module can significantly reduce the workload of data labelling [17]. Afterwards, more robust seizure detection for the indeterminate subjects is performed by the SL using an Easy Ensemble algorithm. Easy Ensemble, as a class-imbalance learning method, can potentially decrease the generalization error of the seizure-free segments. The proposed method can significantly reduce the workload of data labelling while guaranteeing satisfactory performance. The proposed seizure detection system is evaluated using the Children's Hospital Boston-Massachusetts Institute of Technology (CHB-MIT) scalp EEG dataset, and it achieves a mean accuracy of 92.62%, a mean sensitivity of 95.55%, and a mean specificity of 92.57%.

Y. R. Aldana, et.al (2019) proposes a method to detect nonconvulsive seizures for a further nonconvulsive status epilepticus diagnosis [18]. To differentiate between the normal and seizure electroencephalogram (EEG), a K-Nearest Neighbor, a Radial Basis Support Vector Machine, and a Linear Discriminant Analysis classifier are used. The classifier features are obtained from the Canonical Polyadic Decomposition (CPD) and Block Term Decomposition of the EEG data represented as third order tensor. The experimental results suggest that a Hilbert-Huang tensor representation and the CPD analysis provide the most suitable framework for nonconvulsive seizure detection. The Radial Basis Support Vector Machine classifier shows the best performance with sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy values over 98%.

Z. Chen, et.al (2020) develop a unified framework for early epileptic seizure detection and epilepsy diagnosis, which includes two phases [19]. In the first phase, the signal intensity is first calculated for each data point of the given EEG, enabling the well-known autoregressive moving average (ARMA) model to characterize the dynamic behavior of the EEG time series. In the second phase, we use pattern recognition technique to classify the suspicious EEG segments. propose a new and practical classifier based on a pairwise of one-class SVMs for epilepsy diagnosis. We conducted experiments on the publicly-available Bern-Barcelona and CHB-MIT EEG database, respectively, to validate the effectiveness of the proposed framework, and our method achieved classification accuracy of 93% and 94% on them. Comprehensive experimental results, outperforming the state-of-the-arts, suggest its great potentials in real applications.

J. Mu, et.al (2021) An automatic epileptic seizure detection method with graph-regularized non-negative matrix factorization (GNMF) and Bayesian linear discriminate analysis (BLDA) is presented in this paper [20]. First, discrete wavelet decomposition is applied to analyze raw electroencephalogram (EEG) signals, and the normalization based on differential operator is used to guarantee the nonnegative constraint and reinforce the distinction between seizure and non-seizure signals. Then, GNMF is employed to dimensionality reduction and feature extraction for EEG data, which could capture a parts-based representation of samples and obtain more discriminative features. The EEG features are calculated and entered into the BLDA classifier for categorized results. The public Freiburg EEG database is used to evaluate the performance of the proposed seizure detection method. The results showed event-based sensitivity of 95.24%, epoch-based sensitivity of 93.20%, and a false-alarm rate of 0.5/h. These results demonstrate the potential clinical value of this method for automatic seizure detection.

Table 2.2

Author	Year	Technique Used	Findings	Limitations
Y. Guo, et.al	2022	a hybrid system	This system achieves a mean accuracy of 92.62%, a mean sensitivity of 95.55%, and a mean specificity of 92.57%.	The specific seizure type information is not available in sufficient amount. Thus, the link of result of seizure type is not attained.
Y. R. Aldana, et.al	2019	K-Nearest Neighbor, a Radial Basis Support Vector Machine, and a Linear Discriminant Analysis	The Radial Basis Support Vector Machine classifier shows the best performance with sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy values over 98%.	The uncertainty in the classification task was maximized when the number of factors was increased.
Z. Chen, et.al	2020	a unified framework	our method achieved classification accuracy of 93% and 94% on them. Comprehensive experimental results, outperforming the state-of-the-arts, suggest its great potentials in real applications.	The attributes extracted and used EEG signal representation are small in amount due to which the efficacy is mitigated.
J. Mu, et.al	2021	An automatic epileptic seizure detection method	The results showed event-based sensitivity of 95.24%, epoch-based sensitivity of 93.20%, and a false-alarm rate of 0.5/h.	The dataset utilized in this approach contained restricted EEG recordings

2.3 Epileptic Seizures Detection Using Optimization Techniques

S. K. Mohapatra, et.al (2022) a new enhanced search ability based ASO named as ESAASO is proposed [21]. In this study, inertia weight, levy flight and ranking strategies are integrated into ASO to improve the search performance. The proposed method has been studied on CHB-MIT scalp EEG database. There are 13 number of features are extracted by using TQWT and features are selected using genetic algorithm (GA). The proposed detection method has been computed using twelve well known optimization algorithms with LSSVM classifier. We have obtained average accuracy, sensitivity, selectivity, specificity, average detection rate, G-Mean and area under curve (AUC) values as 98.37%, 91.11%, 91.67%, 91.46%, 91.28%, 91.28% and 0.992 respectively using 10-fold cross-validation method. The proposed algorithm is found outperform as compared to conventional ASO for seizure and non-seizure detection.

A. S. Eltrass, et.al (2021) proposes a new automated real-time approach for EEG epileptic seizure detection based on serial concatenation of Quantized Kernel Least Mean Square (QKLMS) adaptive filters [22]. The QKLMS filter is employed in the proposed system to achieve accurate real-time diagnosis with low hardware complexity. The Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO) algorithm is employed to find the optimum values of the energy threshold and the parameters of the QKLMS algorithm. The experimental results show that the proposed epileptic seizure detection system outperforms other state-of-the-art systems with an accuracy of 97.88 %, sensitivity of 98.80 %, specificity of 97.65 %, and computational time of 0.58 sec. This demonstrates that the proposed approach can be used to assist neurologists in enhancing the accuracy of epileptic seizure detection.

S. Yuan, et.al (2022) An automatic detection of epileptic seizure method based on kernel-based robust probabilistic collaborative representation (ProCRC) combined with graph-regularized non-negative matrix factorization (GNMF) is proposed in this work [23]. The raw EEG signals are pre-processed through the wavelet transform to obtain time-frequency distribution of EEG signals as preliminary feature information and GNMF is further employed for dimension reduction, retaining and enhancing the productive feature information of EEG signals. Then, the test sample is represented using robust ProCRC that can decide whether the testing sample belongs to each class (seizure or non-seizure) by jointly maximizing the likelihood. Finally, post-processing techniques are introduced to generate more accurate and reliable results. The average epoch-based sensitivity of 96.48%, event-based sensitivity of 93.65% and specificity of 98.55% are acquired in this method, which is evaluated on the public Freiburg EEG database.

Table 2.3

Author	Year	Technique Used	Findings	Limitations
S. K. Mohapatra, et.al	2022	ESAASO	We have obtained average accuracy, sensitivity, selectivity, specificity, average detection rate, G-Mean and area under curve (AUC) values as 98.37%, 91.11%, 91.67%, 91.46%, 91.28%, 91.28% and 0.992 respectively using 10-fold cross-validation method.	The recall is found lower on the large sized EEG datasets.
A. S. Eltrass, et.al	2021	a new automated real-time approach	The experimental results show that the proposed epileptic seizure detection system outperforms other state-of-the-art systems with an accuracy of 97.88 %, sensitivity of 98.80 %, specificity of 97.65 %, and computational time of 0.58 sec.	The transparency and explainability is not present properly and it leads to alleviate the trust in the decisions making while diagnosing epileptic seizure.
S. Yuan, et.al	2022	An automatic detection of epileptic seizure method	The average epoch-based sensitivity of 96.48%, event-based sensitivity of 93.65% and specificity of 98.55% are acquired in this method	The scope of this work is limited to this approach only.

Conclusion

Automated seizure detection has been an active field of research for the past three decades. Most importantly, given that seizure characteristics vary among different patients and may change over time, automatically extracting and learning informative features from EEG data is necessary. Most algorithms follow a two-stage machine learning pipeline consisting of feature extraction from the EEG signal over short time windows, followed by a binary classifier to identify seizure versus non-seizure intervals. The probabilistic models are the most efficient models for the seizure prediction. In future, Hybrid probabilistic model can be designed for the seizure prediction.

References

- [1] Y. Qin, C. Han, M. Lu, R. Wang, L. Yang and Y. Che, "Automatic Detection of Seizures Using Extreme Learning Machine with a Single Feature," 2018 37th Chinese Control Conference (CCC), 2018, pp. 4430-4433
- [2] A. Shankar, S. Dandapat and S. Barma, "Seizure Type Classification Using EEG Based on Gramian Angular Field Transformation and Deep Learning," 2021 43rd Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine & Biology Society (EMBC), 2021, pp. 3340-3343

- [3] S. Dora, B. Rangarajan, K. Subramanian and S. Suresh, "Automatic seizure detection in multichannel EEG using McCIT2FIS approach," 2015 IEEE International Conference on Fuzzy Systems (FUZZ-IEEE), 2015, pp. 1-8
- [4] M. S. J. Solaija, S. Saleem, K. Khurshid, S. A. Hassan and A. M. Kamboh, "Dynamic Mode Decomposition Based Epileptic Seizure Detection from Scalp EEG," in IEEE Access, vol. 6, pp. 38683-38692, 2018
- [5] M. Li, X. Sun, W. Chen, Y. Jiang and T. Zhang, "Classification Epileptic Seizures in EEG Using Time-Frequency Image and Block Texture Features," in IEEE Access, vol. 8, pp. 9770-9781, 2020
- [6] L. K. Jayashree and B. Venkateswarlu, "EEG Signals in Epilepsy Seizure Detection: An Empirical Study," 2020 4th International Conference on Electronics, Communication and Aerospace Technology (ICECA), 2020, pp. 295-300
- [7] A. Nandy, M. A. Alahe, S. M. Nasim Uddin, S. Alam, A. -A. Nahid and M. A. Awal, "Feature Extraction and Classification of EEG Signals for Seizure Detection," 2019 International Conference on Robotics, Electrical and Signal Processing Techniques (ICREST), 2019, pp. 480-485
- [8] P. Yaswanth, A. S. Pranav and R. I. Minu, "Automatic Seizure Classification using CNN," 2020 International Conference on Communication and Signal Processing (ICCSP), 2020, pp. 0743-0745
- [9] F. Manzouri, L. Khurana, K. Kravalis, T. Stieglitz, A. Schulze-Bonhage and M. Dümpelmann, "An Optimized EEG-Based Seizure Detection Algorithm for Implantable Devices," 2021 10th International IEEE/EMBS Conference on Neural Engineering (NER), 2021, pp. 995-998
- [10] T. Tao, L. Guo, Q. He, H. Zhang and L. Xu, "Seizure detection by brain-connectivity analysis using dynamic graph isomorphism network," 2022 44th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine & Biology Society (EMBC), 2022, pp. 2302-2305
- [11] M. YAKOUBI, R. HAMDI and M. B. SALAH, "Automatic identification and analysis of epileptic seizure," 2019 6th International Conference on Image and Signal Processing and their Applications (ISPA), 2019, pp. 1-5,
- [12] M. H. Ahmad Yarandi, M. A. Tehrani and S. H. Sardouie, "Automatic Epileptic Seizure Detection: Graph Features Versus Graph Kernels," 2021 7th International Conference on Signal Processing and Intelligent Systems (ICSPIS), 2021, pp. 1-5
- [13] C. Huang, W. Chen and G. Cao, "Automatic Epileptic Seizure Detection via Attention-Based CNN-BiRNN," 2019 IEEE International Conference on Bioinformatics and Biomedicine (BIBM), 2019, pp. 660-663
- [14] J. Craley, E. Johnson and A. Venkataraman, "Integrating Convolutional Neural Networks and Probabilistic Graphical Modeling for Epileptic Seizure Detection in Multichannel EEG", Springer, vol. 1, no. 13, pp. 291–303, 2019
- [15] A. A. E. Shoka, M. M. Dessouky and E. E-D. Hemdan, "An efficient CNN based epileptic seizures detection framework using encrypted EEG signals for secure telemedicine applications", Alexandria Engineering Journal, vol. 32, no. 4, pp. 1703-1712, 12 October 2022
- [16] X. Zhang, L. Yao, M. Dong, Z. Liu, Y. Zhang and Y. Li, "Adversarial Representation Learning for Robust Patient-Independent Epileptic Seizure Detection," in IEEE Journal of Biomedical and Health Informatics, vol. 24, no. 10, pp. 2852-2859, Oct. 2020

- [17] Y. Guo et al., "Epileptic Seizure Detection by Cascading Isolation Forest-Based Anomaly Screening and EasyEnsemble," in *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering*, vol. 30, pp. 915-924, 2022
- [18] Y. R. Aldana, B. Hunyadi, E. J. M. Reyes, V. R. Rodríguez and S. Van Huffel, "Nonconvulsive Epileptic Seizure Detection in Scalp EEG Using Multiway Data Analysis," in *IEEE Journal of Biomedical and Health Informatics*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 660-671, March 2019
- [19] Z. Chen, G. Lu, Z. Xie and W. Shang, "A Unified Framework and Method for EEG-Based Early Epileptic Seizure Detection and Epilepsy Diagnosis," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 20080-20092, 2020
- [20] J. Mu, L. Dai and S. Yuan, "Automatic detection for epileptic seizure using graph-regularized nonnegative matrix factorization and Bayesian linear discriminate analysis", *Biocybernetics and Biomedical Engineering*, vol. 21, no. 14, pp. 922-924, 8 September 2021
- [21] S. K. Mohapatra and S. Patnaik, "ESA-ASO: An enhanced search ability based atom search optimization algorithm for epileptic seizure detection", *Measurement: Sensors*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 73191-73199, 29 October 2022
- [22] A. S. Eltrass, M. B. Tayel and A. F. EL-qady, "Automatic epileptic seizure detection approach based on multi-stage Quantized Kernel Least Mean Square filters", *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control*, vol. 28, no. 10, pp. 2325-2332, 16 August 2021
- [23] S. Yuan et al., "Automatic Epileptic Seizure Detection Using Graph-Regularized Non-Negative Matrix Factorization and Kernel-Based Robust Probabilistic Collaborative Representation," in *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering*, vol. 30, pp. 2641-2650, 2022
- [24] Binnie, C.D., De Korte, R.A. and Wisman, T., 1979. Fluorescent lighting and epilepsy. *Epilepsia*, 20(6), pp.725-727.
- [25] Wilkins, A., Veitch, J. and Lehman, B., 2010, September. LED lighting flicker and potential health concerns: IEEE standard PAR1789 update. In 2010 IEEE Energy Conversion Congress and Exposition (pp. 171-178). IEEE.
- [26] Harding, G.F. and Jeavons, P.M., 1994. Photosensitive epilepsy (No. 133). Cambridge University Press.
- [27] Ehlers, C.L. and Killam, E.K., 1982. The effects of constant light on EEG and seizure activity in the epileptic baboon. *Electroencephalography and Clinical Neurophysiology*, 54(2), pp.187-193.
- [28] Piccioli, M., Vigeveno, F., Buttinelli, C. and Trenité, D.G.K.N., 2005. Do video games evoke specific types of epileptic seizures?. *Epilepsy & Behavior*, 7(3), pp.524-530.
- [29] Morimoto, T., Hayakawa, T., Sugie, H., Awaya, Y. and Fukuyama, Y., 1985. Epileptic seizures precipitated by constant light, movement in daily life, and hot water immersion. *Epilepsia*, 26(3), pp.237-242.
- [30] Goodkind, R., 1936. Myoclonic and epileptic attacks precipitated by bright light. *Archives of Neurology & Psychiatry*, 35(4), pp.868-875.
- [31] Gastaut, H. and Regis, H., 1961. On the Subject of Lennox's "Akinetic" Petit Mal. In Memory of WG Lennox. *Epilepsia*, 2(4), pp.298-305.
- [32] Strauss, H., 1940. Jacksonian seizures of reflex origin. *Archives of Neurology & Psychiatry*, 44(1), pp.140-152.